

Diagrams for Health & Wellness and Infographics

The Detoxification Health and Wellness Medicine for the body
Natural Health & Functional Medicine

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Detoxification

Detoxification

Colon Lungs
Kidney Intestine Purge
& Excrete trash out
of the body!

The Digestive system

The human digestive system breaks food down into small molecules that can be used by cells in the body.

Image from OpenStax, CC BY 4.0

Digestion can be a complicated process, yet the human body does it very masterfully. One way to look at it is like an orchestra in complete harmony. This is what the digestive and excretion process goes through. Digestion begins when food enters the mouth, imagine your favorite piece of steak to be chewed up (oral cavity). Both mechanical and chemical digestion occur in the mouth. Teeth grind and break up food (mechanical), while an enzyme in saliva called amylase begins to break down carbohydrates (chemical).

After it is swallowed, the chewed food (now called a bolus) moves down the esophagus. The esophagus acts as a connection between the mouth and the stomach, but no digestion occurs here.

The bolus then reaches the stomach, where more mechanical and chemical digestion take place. The muscles in the stomach walls churn the bolus (mechanical), allowing it to mix with digestive enzymes and gastric acids (chemical). This process converts the bolus into a liquid called chyme.

Digestion continues in the stomach for several hours. During this time, an enzyme called pepsin breaks down most of the protein in the food.

Image from OpenStax, CC BY 4.0

The chyme is slowly transported into the small intestine, where most chemical digestion takes place. Bile, which is made in the liver, is released from the gallbladder to help digest fats. In addition, enzymes from the pancreas and intestinal walls combine with the chyme to start the final part of digestion.

Most nutrient absorption occurs in the small intestine. Nutrients are absorbed through its walls into the circulatory system and by the time the chyme exits the small intestine, only water and undigestible substances are left behind.

The chyme then enters the large intestine. Here, water is removed and bacteria break down some undigestible materials, producing important compounds (such as vitamin K). The concentrated waste material that remains is called feces, which is passed into the rectum and eliminated from the body through the anus.

Accessory organs

Accessory organs help with digestion but are not part of the digestive tract. These include:

Salivary glands: moisten food and begin chemical digestion of starches.

Liver: creates bile for fat digestion, detoxifies blood, processes absorbed vitamins

Gallbladder: stores bile produced by the liver

Pancreas: secretes pancreatic juices to help digestion of proteins and carbohydrates

The Excretory system

The excretory system removes metabolic wastes from the body.

The major organs of excretion are the kidneys, a pair of bean-shaped organs located below the liver. The kidneys filter blood and regulate water balance in the body.

There are several other organs that are also involved in excretion, including:

the skin, which removes excess water and salt via sweat,

the lungs, which exhale carbon dioxide, and

the liver, which breaks down toxic substances in the blood and convert nitrogenous waste into urea

Urinary tract

The urinary tract is a major part of the excretory system. It filters wastes and water from the blood, and eliminates them from the body.

Wikimedia, Public domain

The kidneys produce a waste product called urine using special functional units called nephrons. The urine is then excreted from the body. This process takes place in three steps:

Filtration: Blood enters a nephron, which filters out impurities.

Reabsorption: The impurities move through tubules, while the rest of the blood is reabsorbed through capillary walls into the blood.

Excretion: Urine is transported from the kidneys through the ureters and into the urinary bladder. It remains stored in the bladder until it is released through the urethra.

Take a closer look!

Digestion does not begin in the stomach. While some digestion occurs in the stomach, the process actually begins in the mouth, where chewing and salivary amylase act on the food.

The digestive system does not produce urine. Some people think that the digestive system has two outlets - one for feces and one for urine. However, urine is a product of the excretory system, not the digestive system.

The small intestine is actually longer than the large intestine. In fact, at approximately 20 feet in length, the small intestine is nearly four times as long as the large intestine (5 feet long)! However, the intestines are named for their diameters, not their lengths. The large intestine has a diameter of about 3 inches compared to the small intestine, with a diameter of about 1 inch.

Fatigue - Your fatigue can be a sign of dehydration. Whether you're working out or working a desk job, your body needs water to work well and keep cool. If you're thirsty, you're already dehydrated. Fix: Drink water throughout the day so your urine is light colored.

Tired or Fatigued?

Human Vein and Artery Anatomy

Chimeric Antigen Receptor Therapy

**Collect white blood cells
patient apheresis**

**Activate and Isolate
Day 0**

**Transduce
Day 1**

Grow

**Infuse patient with
engineered CART cells**

Car T therapy (Cellular therapy)

Core engineering elements of Cart T therapy are fundamental to patient's cells

Isolate T cells and Transfer genetic material into T- cell called Transduction

Grow engineered T cells in special media this makes them increase in number so they are able to attack and kill the cancer cells once infused back into the patient. The science leverages our own natural biology.

NHL bullet points and stats

- -Designed to fight cancer NHL
- -Lymphocytes change and grow out of control
- -Cancer cells have no positive purpose in the body and take up space

2014 662,000 people are living with Non- Hodgkins Lymphoma

73,000 new cases are diagnosed

2.1% roughly 6.600,000 people will be diagnosed with NHL

October 18, 2017 FDA approval Thomas Sandoval rare form of lymphoma male immunology therapy car T.

Normally immune cells good at fighting sickness bacteria but not cancer. own cells are removed from the body reprogrammed to find and kill cancer cells and supped up GPS navigation on the cell and kill the lymphoma after being infused back in. Frederick Lock Medical Oncologist led the clinical trial after single treatment 39 percent had no more lymphoma. Side effects was flu- like symptoms and confusion and treatment related deaths.

Laguna Beach California, a woman Dr. John Timmerman of UCLA explained in media interview failed all their therapies 82% saw cells shrink. 30 tumors she had and all was shrunk and learning curb was involved from doctors.

Collect patient's white blood cells (Apheresis)

The process they call a vein to vein process Apheresis material is taken from the patient and shipped to the manufacturing facility in a temperature controlled box called a Nanocool.

0- Day T cells isolated and enriched with special media T cells are activated to prepare for transduction. Isolate—Activate

1- Activated T cells are transduced with the anti-CD19 CAR fragment

Days and Harvest Day

Transduced cells are incubated for several days to grow and expand. Once dose is achieved, the final product is washed and frozen.

After quality acceptance confirmed sent back to treatment site in temperature monitored cryogenic shipper. Patient infused with their own T-cells. Within the patient's body, the CART cells do their job to kill the cancer cells until the tumors are gone.

Preparing for treatment

Patient blood is collected through an intravenous tube in one arm

Blood passes through apheresis machine, which separates the cells from the blood.

Cells packaged according to procedure and sent to the Kite facility

The remainder of the blood is returned through intravenous tube in the other arm

The nanocool box has a temp tell box so temp stays good while in transport (resembles a remote).

CAR T cells engineered the low down process

Cell therapy is in El Segundo in immunotherapy finding a cure for cancer , this is personalized medicine state of the art facility is needed. 4- 5 thousand patients are the patient load as the patients load increases vein to vein in 14 days. They have lives in their hands. Speed and quality with the cells to modify and inherit to use the facility to target the tumor cells. This is the beginning of cell therapy treatment.

Isolate cells in Sepax closed system protects from infection cells isolated according to density.

Enriched with special media activated and washed in Sepax separation device . This is cell processing and plasma extraction. Buffy coat extraction & RBC extraction Golden standard in stem cell processing. Adult stem cell banking and Regenerative Medicine.

Cells now sampled and tested BSC Biological safety cabinet. A precision small amount of isolated cells to next step for activation at nucleo counter for exact number cell count. Nucleo counter 200 Vial cassette for exact count.

Extra cells are frozen cryo preservation until needed. Ultra low temperatures.

CD3 receptors + anti CD3 anti bodies, with CD-28.

Cells for Transduction Retronectin reagent brings vector together with the T cells so the anti CD19 fragment is inserted into the T Cell.

Cell expansion from curve of time and log of expanded cell number.

Final product formulation final wash and sampled and cryo preserved until patient ready to receive them. All leading to a single infusion for dramatic tumor shrinkage.

Immunotherapy

Absorption- The process by which nutrients pass through the walls of the digestive system into the blood

Chemical digestion -The breaking down of food using chemical agents, such as enzymes and bile

Digestive system -The body system that converts food into energy and nutrients to fuel the body

Detoxification- Cleansing of the body mind body soul and spirit; purging pushing out of toxic substances and things not health for the human body.

Kidney Intestine Colon Gastric System- The GI tract is a series of hollow organs joined in a long, twisting tube from the mouth to the anus. The hollow organs that make up the GI tract are the mouth, esophagus, stomach, small intestine, large intestine, and anus. The liver, pancreas, and gallbladder are the solid organs of the digestive system

Excretion Excretion gets rid of carbon dioxide, water, and other, possibly harmful, substances from your body. Your lungs excrete carbon dioxide as you breathe out, your kidneys filter out nasties to produce urine, removing nitrogen waste from your body, and your skin sheds excess salt through sweat.

Excretory system The body system that removes metabolic wastes from the body

Liquid nutrients Vitamins and Minerals - Drinking fresh fruit and vegetable juices, smoothies, water, and tea. Drinking only specific liquids, such as salted water or lemon juice.

Anatomy Vein and Artery - Your arteries and veins have a big job to do. They're part of a transportation system that moves blood around. Arteries carry blood loaded with oxygen from your heart to the rest of your body. Veins deliver the blood, now without much of the oxygen, back to your heart.

CAR T Cell Therapy - CAR T- Cell therapy is a form of immunotherapy that uses specially altered T cells — a part of the immune system — to fight cancer. A sample of a patient's T cells are collected from the blood, then modified to produce special structures called chimeric antigen receptors (CARs) on their surface.

Immunotherapy - Immunotherapy is treatment that uses certain parts of a person's immune system to fight diseases such as cancer. This can be done in a couple of ways: Stimulating, or boosting, the natural defenses of your immune system so it works harder or smarter to find and attack cancer cells.

Gallbladder. Your gallbladder stores bile between meals. When you eat, your gallbladder squeezes bile through the bile ducts into your small intestine.

Small intestine. Your small intestine makes digestive juice, which mixes with bile and pancreatic juice to complete the breakdown of proteins, carbohydrates, and fats. Bacteria in your small intestine make some of the enzymes you need to digest carbohydrates. Your small intestine moves water from your bloodstream into your GI tract to help break down food. Your small intestine also absorbs water with other nutrients.

4Healing Natural

By: Dr. David Render

Nutrition Facts	
Serving Size oz.	
Serving Per Container	
Amount Per Serving:	
Calories	Calories From Fat
	% Daily value*
Total Fat	%
Saturated Fat	%
Trans Fat	
Cholesterol	%
Sodium	%
Total Carbohydrate	%
Dietary Fiber	%
Sugars	
Protein	

*Percent Daily values are based on a 2000 calorie diet. Your daily values may be higher or lower depending on your calorie needs.

Nutrition Facts	
Serving Size 10 oz.	
Serving Per Container 5	
Amount Per Serving	
Calories 200	Calories From Fat 200
	% Daily value*
Total Fat 10 g	35%
Saturated Fat 1.5g	11%
Trans Fat 0.0 g	
Cholesterol 0 mg	1%
Sodium 210 mg	15%
Total Carbohydrate 15 g	3%
Dietary Fiber 2 g	3%
Sugars 3 g	
Protein 30 g	
Vitamin A 3%	Vitamin C 3%
Calcium 6%	Iron 6%

*Percent Daily values are based on a 2000 calorie diet. Your daily values may be higher or lower depending on your calorie needs.

4 Healing Natural

Nutrition Facts	
Serving Size oz.	
Serving Per Container	
Amount Per Serving:	
Calories	Calories From Fat
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Sodium	%
Total Carbohydrate	%
Dietary Fiber	%
Sugars	
Protein	

*Percent Daily values are based on a 2000 calorie diet. Your daily values may vary depending on your calorie needs.

Nutrition Facts	
Serving Size 10 oz.	
Serving Per Container 5	
Amount Per Serving	
Calories 200	Calories From Fat 200
	% Daily value*
Total Fat 10 g	35%
Saturated Fat 1.5g	11%
Trans Fat 0.0 g	
Cholesterol 0 mg	1%
Sodium 210 mg	15%
Total Carbohydrate 15 g	3%
Dietary Fiber 2 g	3%
Sugars 3 g	
Protein 30 g	
Vitamin A 3%	• Vitamin C 3%
Calcium 6%	• Iron 6%

*Percent Daily values are based on a 2000 calorie diet. Your daily values may vary depending on your calorie needs.

Perfect Hummus

Puree the chickpeas, garlic put herbs on top
and enjoy

Milk Dairy Free Alternatives

1 cup per serving

Flax

Soy

Oak

Pea

Almond

Coconut

Nitrate Rich Foods

Arugula

Basil

Beets

Cilantro

Rhubarb

**Nitrates bring relaxation to the blood vessels,
improve blood vessels and deliver more oxygen to blood
vessels**

Vegetable Bowl

Vegetable bowl can have
Rice Red Onion
Beans Tahini
Olives Tomatoes

4Healing

Seeds and Bowl Toppings

Pumpkin Seeds

high in Iron and
Magnesium

Hemp

High in protein

Raisins

High in Copper and
Calories

Almond Butter

High in protein & Zinc

Salad bowl >>>

Tomatoes
Vitamin C & A

Lentils Iron &
Protein

Onions Manganese
Vitamin B6

Kale Vitamin C & A

Bananas 101

High antioxidant content & digest quickly and sweeter and contain more sugar than green bananas

Prebiotic & High Amount of resistant starch nondigestible fibers maybe harsh on your digestive system

Greatest nutrients and mineral loss sweet and digestible

Chia pudding

Chia
Seeds

Plant Milk

Toppings

Combine the ingredients & Refrigerate
Overnight Top with Toppings
Enjoy

Rich Protein Vegetables

Green Peas

Alfalfa Sprouts

Brussel Sprouts

Sweet Corn

Collard Greens

Artichokes

Mustard
Greens

Broccoli

Legumes Protein Rich

Kidney Beans

Edamame

Mung Beans

White Beans

Black beans

Chick peas

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